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CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE

Bayero University, Kano – Nigeria

... an Africa Centre of Excellence in Dryland Agriculture

VISION

Resilient and Prosperous African Drylands

MISSION

To improve livelihood, resilience and sustainable use of natural resources in African drylands through training and demand-driven research

CORE VALUES

- Good leadership and Inclusiveness
- Passion and Teamwork
- Commitment and Sacrifice
- Integrity and Transparency
- Professionalism and Excellence

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CDA's Farm Produce Retail Outlet Commissioned

A retail outlet tagged “Fresh from the Farm” belonging to the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) that will provide fresh vegetables and other farm produce for members of the University community and neighbouring communities was commissioned on Friday, 18th September, 2020.

The vegetables and other produce are being harvested from the CDA Research and Training Farm.

“This outlet will enormously benefit staff, students and other members of the neighbouring communities with healthy and fresh vegetables on daily basis,” said the Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas, who commissioned the retail outlet.

The Vice Chancellor noted that “we have started reaping the fruits of CDA Farm in which members of the University Community can get access to fresh farm produce without going outside the University.”

He congratulated the CDA for establishing the outlet and said that the University would borrow a leaf from the centre to establish its farm.

In his remarks earlier, the Director, CDA, Professor Jibrin Muhammad Jibrin, said the idea to establish the farm was conceived in 2014 aimed at exposing students to modern farming practises and facilities.

The Director explained that “a lot of problems were encountered in Nigeria for the establishment of research and training farm, as experts were brought from Brazil and Israel by various institutions to establish such gigantic projects, but usually they soon collapsed due to lack of local expertise.

“We sought advice from different stakeholders and invited experts and professionals in the field who helped us to set up our farm,” the Director explained.

According to him, the farm was basically established for research and training purposes, but

because of sustainability sake beyond the Africa Centre of Excellence (ACE) project, the Centre embarked on commercial production.

The Deputy Director Outreach and Publication, Professor Amina Mustapha expressed gratitude to the Vice Chancellor, Principal Officers and all other staff of the University that attended the ceremony.

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Minister of Environment Visits CDA, Pledges Support to BUK

The Honourable Minister of Environment, Dr Mohammed Mahmud Abubakar, visited the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) on Saturday 19th September, 2020. He was accompanied by the Director-General of the National Agency for the Great Green Wall (NAGGW), Alhaji Bukar Hassan. The Minister and his team toured the CDA Training and Research Farm, Central Laboratory, Molecular Biology Laboratory, Food Analysis Laboratory, Tissue Culture Facility and the newly commissioned CDA Retail Outlet.

In his welcoming remarks, the Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas, thanked the Minister for his visit and for the support of the Ministry of Environment to BUK, especially the solar power projects which have assisted the University in ensuring more steady power supply.

The Director of CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, while taking the Minister and his team round the facilities in CDA, explained the various synergistic roles the CDA could play with various agencies of the Federal Ministry of environment, especially NAGGW.

The Minister congratulated Professor Sagir Abbas on his recent appointment as the Vice Chancellor and said he was glad that he accepted the invitation to visit CDA.

According to the Minister "I have heard a lot of positive things about BUK. I am really impressed with what is happening here. We will do everything we can to support the University". He added that he had wanted to personally come for the launching of the CDA ACE-Impact project in December 2019, but could not due to exigencies of his work. He requested the DG NAGGW to actively work with CDA in addressing the various issues in drylands of Nigeria. He also promised to link CDA with other agencies of the Federal Ministry of Environment so that they take advantage of the cutting-edge laboratory services available in the centre.

The DG of NAGGW, Alhaji Bukar Hassan, remarked that the visions and missions of NAGGW and CDA are very closely aligned. He promised to engage CDA in the Agency's activities, especially in raising tissue culture and disease-free seedlings for its afforestation programmes. He further stated that the Agency has currently engaged Bayero University Consultancy Services to establish shelterbelts and woodlots in Jigawa State.

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CDA Harvests Grapes, Banana ...Embarks on Commercial Production

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture's Research and Training Farm has commenced the harvest of banana and planned to harvest grapes before the end of the year 2020. The Centre has also renewed its plan to embark on commercial activities to sustain itself beyond the Africa Centres of Excellence (ACEs) project period.

At present, the Centre's farm has over 2,000 stands of mango which will provide steady income for many years to come. This is in addition to many other crops such as guava, oranges being planted.

Already, the farm provides fresh vegetables to the members of the University Community and beyond on daily basis, as the CDA's Fresh from the farm Retail

Outlet remains a point for purchase of farm produce and other poultry products.

"We are multiplying more bananas at our Tissue Culture Laboratory and we have banana seedlings for farmers who want to grow them," said the Director, CDA, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin.

According to him, "our grape and guava each occupies almost one hectre and will be in the market before the end of the year," he said.

The Director, who spoke at the commissioning of CDA Retail Outlet for fresh vegetables and other farm produce, explained that the farm has tomatoes in abundance at green house, noting that during rainy season many grains were also planted.

CDA Partners Seed Companies to Boost Groundnut Production in Nigeria

Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) has partnered seed companies to boost the production of groundnut and revive it to be among the mainstay of the Nigeria's economy.

Nigeria used to be the highest groundnut exporting country in Africa, but a combination of drought, rosette and other diseases wiped out groundnut production in the 1970s and early 1980s.

The CDA is currently a stakeholder in the Accelerated Varietal Improvement and Seed Delivery of Legumes and Cereals in Africa (AVISA) Project, which aims to increase productivity, profitability, resilience and marketability of nutritious grain legume and cereal crops: Groundnut, Cowpea, Common Bean, Millet and Sorghum in 7 African Countries.

CDA Produces basic seeds and engages relevant stakeholders to produce other classes of seeds. In the

current rainy season, it planted 5.77ha of basic (1.83ha breeder and 3.9ha foundation) seeds.

The CDA also established hundreds of demonstration plots (approximately 300m square) to showcase the potentials of the improved groundnut varieties and large acreage for commercial seed production.

On Tuesday, 29th September, 2020, the CDA interacted with seed companies and took them round to see different variety of seeds- SAMNUT 27, SAMNUT 28 and SAMNUT 29, as well as Foundation seeds of SAMNUT 24, SAMNUT 25 and SAMNUT 26.

According to the Director, Training, Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed, who took the seed companies round the groundnut seed farms, said ICRISAT and Institute of Agricultural Research in collaboration with CDA have developed and released new improved high-yielding varieties with combined resistance to major biotic stresses.

He said the Centre has engaged the farmers and seed companies to demonstrate what it is doing in order to appreciate its enormous contributions to the development of groundnut farming.

The Deputy Director explained that there are different innovations through technological advancement that led to the production of disease resistant seeds that were used by the farmers with better output, noting that CDA in collaboration with

its partners collaborated to bring the farming of groundnut to the limelight.

During the interaction, the seed companies that include Seeds Project, Innovative Agro Tech, Maina Seeds, Al-Hikma Seeds, KNARDA and many others commended the CDA for its gigantic farm project and reiterated their determination to strengthen their partnership with the centre to boost the groundnut farming in Nigeria.

CDA's FRESH FROM THE FARM

BAYERO UNIVERSITY, KANO

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